

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF PREPARATION STRATEGY IN REDUCING PUBLIC SPEAKING ANXIETY USING THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the effectiveness of preparation strategies in reducing public speaking anxiety among senior high school students. Public speaking anxiety, a common issue in academic settings, impairs students' confidence and oral performance. Despite recognition of various interventions, limited research isolates preparation as a standalone strategy. This study addresses that gap by examining how structured preparation influences anxiety levels across four key dimensions: communication apprehension, test anxiety, fear of negative evaluation, and comfort in speaking English. Using a quasi-experimental design, the study involved Grade 11 students who underwent a three-week intervention. Data were gathered through pre-test and post-test surveys using the Public Speaking Class Anxiety Scale (PSCAS) and analyzed with statistical methods including the Weighted Mean and Mann-Whitney U test. Results showed a significant reduction in three out of four anxiety factors—communication apprehension, test anxiety, and fear of negative evaluation—after the implementation of the preparation strategy. However, comfort in speaking English did not show a statistically significant improvement. The findings indicate that while preparation effectively alleviates most anxiety-related challenges in public speaking, additional interventions may be necessary to enhance language comfort. This study concludes that preparation is a practical and impactful strategy to reduce public speaking anxiety, supporting its integration into educational practices to foster more confident and competent student communicators.

Keywords: *Comfort in Speaking English, Communication Apprehension, Fear of Negative Evaluation, Preparation Strategy, Public Speaking Anxiety, Test Anxiety*

INTRODUCTION

Public Speaking Anxiety (PSA) is one of the social anxieties, and the most feared situation in one's life according to population studies (Ebrahimi et al., 2019). Most Senior High School students graduate without the necessary public speaking skills making them vulnerable to the academic challenges in college where tasks like reports and orals are common (Cuamag, 2024). Fears of mispronunciations, grammar mistakes, or being laughed at by classmates are often the source of such anxieties, and they all have a negative impact on one's performance in class. Research suggests that such anxiety causes avoidance behavior, which in turn leads to reduced student participation and limiting of overall development in language skills (Abdul Jr. et al., 2022). An Indonesian study (Trisanti & Wariyati, 2023) reported that speaking anxiety hampers the English learners leading to low confidence, fear of making errors, and shyness in class which in turn affects language proficiency and calls for the need for effective interventions.

In the Philippines, the use of the English language as the medium of instruction starts in Grade One, which makes it necessary for the students to acquire strong communication skills in the language. Nevertheless, a lot of students go through speaking in English with anxiety, which most of the time leads to disorderly speech, overusing verbal fillers, and unclear expression as a result of language constraints and scattered thoughts, thus all these affect their confidence and ability to get good grades in class significantly. This anxiety is often due to the students' negative past experiences and lack of communication training that academic institutions provide (Pontillas & Talaue, 2021). The development of speaking skills in English is crucial in the process of confidence building and success.

While Alipoyo et. al. (2022) emphasized that students experiencing language anxiety could improve their speaking performance through training, much more of the existing research remained broad and did not deeply explore the specific types of fears students faced when speaking in public. Although public speaking anxiety was a well-documented issue, there was limited empirical evidence on the particular challenges students encountered and the concrete strategies they used to manage these fears (Grieve et al., 2021). This revealed that most of these studies focused on general anxiety without addressing how tailored preparation strategies could reduce anxiety and enhance performance in using the English language.

The researchers of this study aimed to determine how speaking anxiety affected Senior High School students' ability to speak in front of an audience. It focused on preparation strategies using the English language to identify effective ways to reduce anxiety and improve public speaking performance. These strategies helped lessen anxiety symptoms while enhancing students' speaking skills, confidence, and academic performance. The research centered on how preparation could support students in managing anxiety and communicating more effectively in English. This aligned with

Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4), which promotes inclusive and equitable quality education and lifelong learning for all. The study addressed communication barriers and contributed to create a learning environment where students could express themselves confidently and reach their full potential in both academic and real-world settings.

Research Questions

This study determined the effectiveness of the preparation strategy in reducing public speaking anxiety among senior high school students using the English language. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of public speaking anxiety experienced by senior high school students before the implementation of the preparation strategy in terms of the following factors:
 - 1.1. communication apprehension;
 - 1.2. test anxiety;
 - 1.3. fear of negative evaluation; and
 - 1.4. comfort in speaking English?
2. What is the level of public speaking anxiety experienced by senior high school students after the implementation of the preparation strategy in terms of the following factors:
 - 2.1. communication apprehension;
 - 2.2. test anxiety;
 - 2.3. fear of negative evaluation; and
 - 2.4. comfort in speaking English?
3. Is there a significant difference in the level of public speaking anxiety before and after the implementation of the preparation strategy based on the following factors:
 - 3.1. communication apprehension;
 - 3.2. test anxiety;
 - 3.3. fear of negative evaluation; and
 - 3.4. comfort in speaking English?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the level of public speaking anxiety and the demographic profile of senior high school students in terms of:
 - 4.1. age; and
 - 4.2. sex?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study utilized a quasi-experimental research design to assess and establish the effectiveness of a preparation strategy in reducing public speaking anxiety among senior high school students. A pre-test and post-test setup was employed to achieve this purpose. The study focused on a single group of senior high school students from a public secondary institution located in Dumaguete City. These students were introduced to the preparation strategy, and their levels of public speaking anxiety were measured before and after the intervention using a revised version of the Public Speaking Class Anxiety Scale (PSCAS). Originally developed by Yaikhong and Usaha (2012), this instrument

measures four key dimensions of public speaking anxiety: communication apprehension, test anxiety, fear of negative evaluation, and comfort in speaking English.

Research Respondents

The study involved twenty-three (23) Grade 11 students from the STEM B strand of a public secondary school in Dumaguete City. Participants were selected through convenience sampling based on their availability and willingness to participate in the study. These students underwent pre-test and post-test assessments to evaluate the effectiveness of the preparation strategy in reducing their public speaking anxiety.

Research Instruments

The researchers employed a pen-and-paper questionnaire to accommodate all students. The questionnaire consisted of 23 items and was structured as follows:

The questionnaire is divided into 2 parts:

Part 1: Respondent's Demographic Profile. This section contained 3 items that gathered basic information such as name, age, and sex. These details helped explore possible relationships between demographic variables and public speaking anxiety.

Part 2: Public Speaking Class Anxiety Scale (PSCAS). This section contained 20 items adapted and slightly revised from the original PSCAS by Yaikhong and Usaha (2012). The revisions were made to better align the questionnaire with the specific context of the current study. The items measured public speaking anxiety across four key dimensions: communication apprehension, test anxiety, fear of negative evaluation, and comfort in speaking English. Responses were recorded on a five-point Likert scale ranging from "Strongly Agree" to "Strongly Disagree."

To ensure content validity, the revised instrument underwent a validation process involving three experts in the fields of language education and psychological assessment. Each expert reviewed the questionnaire and provided detailed feedback on item relevance, clarity, and alignment with the study objectives. Revisions were made based on their recommendations. After incorporating expert input, the final version of the instrument was reviewed and approved by the researchers' adviser. Lastly, the questionnaire received final endorsement from a statistician to confirm its suitability for data analysis and research implementation.

Research Procedures

The researchers began by securing the necessary approvals through a formal letter signed by their research adviser and submitted to the Dean's Office of the College of Education. Once approved, the letter was forwarded to the Principal of Dumaguete City National High School, requesting permission to conduct the study involving Grade 11 STEM B students. After obtaining authorization, the researchers implemented a three-week experimental procedure held on three consecutive Wednesdays, designed to quantitatively assess the effectiveness of the preparation strategy in reducing public speaking anxiety.

The experimentation commenced on March 12, 2025 (Week 1). During this initial session, the researchers oriented the students by explaining the purpose of the study and introducing public speaking anxiety as the key focus. The preparation strategy was presented as the chosen intervention. Informed consent forms were distributed, signed, and collected. Following this, students participated in introductory public speaking activities, which included delivering self-introductions and narrating a short 3–5 sentence story in English. These tasks simulated public speaking scenarios to help establish a baseline. At the end of the session, the Public Speaking Class Anxiety Scale (PSCAS) was administered to assess participants' initial anxiety levels.

On March 19, 2025 (Week 2), the researchers implemented the preparation strategy. They taught practical techniques such as speech outlining, structured practice and rehearsal, and deep-breathing exercises. Each student was assigned a short speech (1–2 minutes) to prepare using these strategies. Students practiced in pairs or small groups while the researchers provided oversight and support to ensure consistent use of the preparation methods.

The final session was conducted on March 26, 2025 (Week 3). Students delivered their prepared speeches using the techniques they had practiced. After the speaking activity, the PSCAS was re-administered to evaluate the participants' anxiety levels following the intervention. To conclude the experiment, a reflective discussion was held where students shared their experiences on how the preparation strategy impacted their confidence and anxiety. The pre-test and post-test results collected through the PSCAS served as the quantitative data used to assess the effectiveness of the preparation strategy in reducing public speaking anxiety among the participants.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The tools utilized by the researchers for data analysis include:

Weighted Mean. This was utilized in obtaining the level of public speaking anxiety of senior high school students before and after the implementation of the preparation strategy. It measured anxiety in terms of communication apprehension, test anxiety, fear of negative evaluation, and comfort in speaking English.

Mann-Whitney U Test. This was used to determine if there was a significant difference in the level of public speaking anxiety before and after the implementation of the preparation strategy. It helped assess changes in the students' anxiety levels across the four factors mentioned.

Spearman Rank Correlation. This was used to identify the relationship between the age of senior high school students and their level of public speaking anxiety. It measured the strength and direction of the association between these two variables.

Chi-Square Test. This was used to identify the relationship between the sex of senior high school students and their level of public speaking anxiety. It determined

whether there was a significant association between categorical variables (sex and anxiety level).

The following interpretations were applied by the researchers to describe the level of public speaking anxiety among the senior high school students, based on their responses to the Public Speaking Class Anxiety Scale (PSCAS):

Score	Scale	Level of Anxiety (LoA)	Explanation
5	4.21 – 5.00	Very High (VH)	Indicates a very high level of anxiety, showing a strong presence of the factor being assessed.
4	3.41 – 4.20	High (H)	Indicates noticeable anxiety or discomfort, but not extreme.
3	2.61 – 3.40	Moderate (M)	Indicates neither anxious nor relaxed; indifferent or ambivalent.
2	1.81 – 2.60	Low (L)	Indicates a low level of anxiety; feels more at ease speaking English.
1	1.00 – 1.80	Very Low (VL)	Indicates a very low level of anxiety; confident and comfortable speaking English.

Scope and Limitation of the Study

Scope of the Study. This study focused on evaluating the effectiveness of the preparation strategy in reducing public speaking anxiety among senior high school students, specifically Grade 11 STEM Section B, at Dumaguete City National High School (DCNHS) during the academic year 2024–2025. The research examined students' demographic profiles, including age, sex and how these factors influenced the impact of the preparation strategy on public speaking anxiety. The study assessed students' anxiety levels both before and after the implementation of the preparation strategy, focusing on four key factors: communication apprehension, test anxiety, fear of negative evaluation, and comfort in speaking English. A total of twenty-three (23) students from Grade 11 STEM Section B participated in this study. The choice to focus on this specific section was due to the convenience of access and availability, which facilitated smoother data collection and coordination. Moreover, STEM students often encountered situations that required technical presentations and clear communication of complex ideas, making them an ideal group for studying public speaking anxiety. Their curriculum emphasized scientific communication, which aligned with the study's focus on enhancing speaking skills.

Limitations of the Study. There were certain restrictions in this study that were considered when addressing reliability and validity concerns. The number of respondents was limited to twenty-three (23) students from Grade 11 STEM Section B of Dumaguete City National High School (DCNHS), which may not represent the wider population of high school students, limiting the generalizability of the findings. The study focused exclusively on the preparation strategy without exploring other potential methods for

reducing public speaking anxiety. Additionally, the study relied on self-reported data gathered through the Public Speaking Class Anxiety Scale (PSCAS), which may have been subject to response bias. Finally, the timeframe for the study was restricted to three weeks, which may not have allowed for the observation of long-term effects of the intervention on public speaking anxiety.

RESULTS

Table 1.1

Level of Public Speaking Anxiety Experienced by Senior High School Students Prior to the Implementation of the Preparation Strategy in Terms of Communication Apprehension (n=23)

Indicators	w \bar{x}	VD	LoA
1. I struggle to find the right words when speaking in front of a group.	4.22	SA	VH
2. I sensed that certain parts of my body feel very tense and rigid.	4.00	A	H
3. I feel my heart beat faster when speaking in public.	3.91	A	H
4. I feel nervous in front of the class.	3.87	A	H
5. I try to avoid situations where I have to talk in front of others.	3.48	A	H
Composite	3.90	A	H

Table 1.2

Level of Public Speaking Anxiety Experienced by Senior High School Students Prior to the Implementation of the Preparation Strategy in Terms of Test Anxiety (n=23)

Indicators	w \bar{x}	VD	LoA
1. I feel anxious during a graded speech.	4.30	SA	VH
2. I worry about making mistakes during an oral exam.	4.52	SA	VH
3. I feel stressed when delivering a presentation.	3.87	A	H
4. I find it difficult to concentrate during a speaking test.	4.00	A	H
5. I feel overwhelmed before an English-speaking assessment.	4.04	A	H
Composite	4.15	A	H

Table 1.3

Level of Public Speaking Anxiety Experienced by Senior High School Students Prior to the Implementation of the Preparation Strategy in Terms of Fear of Negative Evaluation (n=23)

Indicators	w \bar{x}	V D	Lo A
1. I am afraid that my classmates will laugh at me.	3.5	A	H

2

2. I worry that my teacher will judge me negatively.	4.0	A	H
	9		
3. I hesitate to participate because I fear criticism.	3.7	A	H
	8		
4. I feel embarrassed if I make pronunciation mistakes.	3.7	A	H
	8		
5. I avoid answering questions to prevent making mistakes.	3.3	U	M
	9		
Composite	3.7	A	H
	1		

Table 1.4

Level of Public Speaking Anxiety Experienced by Senior High School Students Prior to the Implementation of the Preparation Strategy in Terms of Comfort in Speaking English (n=23)

Indicators	w \bar{x}	VD	LoA
1. I am willing to take risks and try new vocabulary.	4.22	SA	VH
2. I enjoy practicing and improving speaking skills.	4.13	A	H
3. I feel comfortable initiating conversations in English.	3.52	A	H
4. I feel confident in class.	3.30	U	M
5. I believe I can communicate my ideas.	3.17	U	M
Composite	3.67	A	H

Table 2.1

Level of Public Speaking Anxiety Experienced by Senior High School Students After the Implementation of the Preparation Strategy in Terms of Communication Apprehension (n=23)

Indicators	w \bar{x}	VD	LoA
1. I struggle to find the right words when speaking in front of a group.	3.52	A	H
2. I feel my heart beat faster when speaking in public.	3.39	U	M
3. I feel nervous in front of the class.	3.35	A	H
4. I sensed that certain parts of my body feel very tense and rigid.	3.26	U	M
5. I try to avoid situations where I have to talk in front of others.	3.04	U	M
Composite	3.31	U	M

Table 2.2

Level of Public Speaking Anxiety Experienced by Senior High School Students After the Implementation of the Preparation Strategy in Terms of Test Anxiety (n=23)

Indicators	w \bar{x}	VD	LoA
1. I worry about making mistakes during an oral exam.	3.70	A	H
2. I feel anxious during a graded speech.	3.57	A	H
3. I feel overwhelmed before an English-speaking assessment.	3.57	A	H
4. I feel stressed when delivering a presentation.	3.39	U	M
5. I find it difficult to concentrate during a speaking test.	3.39	U	M
Composite	3.52	A	H

Table 2.3

Level of Public Speaking Anxiety Experienced by Senior High School Students After the Implementation of the Preparation Strategy in Terms of Fear of Negative Evaluation (n=23)

Indicators	w \bar{x}	VD	LoA
1. I hesitate to participate because I fear criticism.	3.43	A	H
2. I worry that my teacher will judge me negatively.	3.35	U	M
3. I feel embarrassed if I make pronunciation mistakes.	3.30	U	M
4. I am afraid that my classmates will laugh at me.	3.17	U	M
5. I avoid answering questions to prevent making mistakes.	2.96	U	M
Composite	3.24	U	M

Table 2.4

Level of Public Speaking Anxiety Experienced by Senior High School Students After the Implementation of the Preparation Strategy in Terms of Comfort in Speaking English (n=23)

Indicators	w \bar{x}	VD	LoA
1. I enjoy practicing and improving my speaking skills.	4.57	SA.	VH
2. I am willing to take risks and try new vocabulary.	4.43	SA	VH
3. I believe I can communicate my ideas clearly.	3.83	A	H
4. I feel confident in class.	3.57	A	H
5. I feel comfortable initiating conversations in English.	3.30	U	M
Composite	3.94	A	H

Table 3.1

Difference in the Perceptions of the Level of Public Speaking Anxiety Before and After the Implementation of the Preparation Strategy in Terms of Communication Apprehension (n = 23)

Variables	Median	U-Value	p-value	Decision	Remark
Communication Apprehension					
Pre-test	4.0	126.5	0.003	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Post-test	3.4				

Table 3.2

Difference in the Perceptions of the Level of Public Speaking Anxiety Before and After the Implementation of the Preparation Strategy in Terms of Test Anxiety (n = 23)

Variables	Median	U-Value	p-value	Decision	Remark
Test Anxiety					
Pre-test	4.2	96	<.001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Post-test	3.6				

Table 3.3

Difference in the Perceptions of the Level of Public Speaking Anxiety Before and After the Implementation of the Preparation Strategy in Terms of Fear of Negative Evaluation (n = 23)

Variables	Median	U-Value	p-value	Decision	Remark
Fear of Negative Evaluation					
Pre-test	3.8	161.5	0.024	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Post-test	3.4				

Table 3.4

Difference in the Perceptions of the Level of Public Speaking Anxiety Before and After the Implementation of the Preparation Strategy in Terms of Comfort in Speaking English (n = 23)

Variable	Median	U-Value	p-value	Decision	Remark
Comfort in Speaking English					
Pre-test	3.8	201.5	0.171	Fail to reject H ₀₁	Not Significant
Post-test	4.0				

Table 4.1

Relationship between the Age of Senior High School Students and the Level of Public Speaking Anxiety (n = 23)

Variables	Computed Value	P-value	Decision	Remark
Age and Overall Level of Public Speaking Anxiety	rs = -0.222	0.310	Fail to reject H_{02}	Not Significant

Table 4.2

Relationship between the Sex of Senior High School Students and the Level of Public Speaking Anxiety (n = 23)

Variables	Computed Value	P-value	Decision	Remark
Sex and Overall Level of Public Speaking Anxiety	$\chi^2 = 1.245$	0.265	Fail to reject H_{02}	Not Significant

DISCUSSION

This section discusses the level of public speaking anxiety experienced by senior high school students before and after the implementation of the preparation strategy, as well as the differences and relationships among selected variables.

The level of public speaking anxiety experienced by students prior to the implementation of the preparation strategy in terms of communication apprehension is presented in **Table 1.1**. The composite mean of 3.90, verbally described as Agree, indicates a high level of communication apprehension among students. This suggests that students generally experience anxiety when speaking in front of others, particularly in organizing and expressing their ideas.

The highest indicator is "I struggle to find the right words when speaking in front of a group," with a weighted mean of 4.22, verbally described as Strongly Agree, indicating a very high level of anxiety. This implies that students have difficulty organizing their thoughts during public speaking. This may be due to a lack of sufficient speaking practice or the pressure of performing, which disrupts their ability to think clearly while speaking. Therefore, students need more structured and consistent speaking activities to help them manage their thoughts under pressure and build speaking confidence. Meanwhile, the lowest indicator is "I try to avoid situations where I have to talk in front of others," with a weighted mean of 3.48, verbally described as Agree, indicating a high level of anxiety. This indicates that while students feel anxious, they do not actively avoid speaking tasks. This could be due to their awareness of the academic importance of public speaking or a willingness to improve despite their discomfort. These behaviors indicate a high level of

communication apprehension, arising from significant internal pressure and fear of negative evaluation, resulting in hesitation and anxiety during public speaking. The apprehension originates from self-doubt and concerns about making mistakes, which lead to avoidance tendencies and difficulties in organizing thoughts during oral communication.

These findings are consistent with Prentiss (2021), who explained that students with high communication apprehension often fear being judged and embarrassed when speaking in public. Fuente et al. (2020) also emphasized that cognitive disruption—such as difficulty thinking clearly—is common in learners who lack regular speaking opportunities. Furthermore, Muftah (2023) found that individuals with high communication apprehension often struggle to communicate effectively, which lowers their confidence in speaking situations.

In addition to communication apprehension, students' public speaking anxiety prior to the intervention was examined in terms of test anxiety, as shown in **Table 1.2**. The composite mean of 4.15 reflects a high level of anxiety related to graded oral activities. Students expressed strong concern about making mistakes during oral examinations, while stress during presentations was relatively lower. This pattern suggests that evaluative pressure intensifies anxiety more than the act of speaking itself.

The highest indicator is “I worry about making mistakes during an oral exam,” which has a weighted mean of 4.52, verbally described as Strongly Agree, indicating a very high level of anxiety. This reveals that students felt intense pressure to perform flawlessly in graded speaking tasks, highlighting the need for anxiety-reducing strategies such as mock oral exams, positive reinforcement, and clear evaluation criteria. This pressure may stem from students' fear of negative judgment or low self-confidence, which increases their worry about making errors. In contrast, the lowest indicator is “I feel stressed when delivering a presentation,” with a weighted mean of 3.87, verbally described as Agree, indicating a high level of anxiety. This demonstrates that while students still felt stress when presenting, it was less severe compared to the anxiety triggered by formal evaluation. This difference likely occurs because, without direct grading, presentations feel less threatening, allowing students to focus more on sharing information than on performance outcomes.

These results support the findings of Chen et al. (2022), who found that speaking assessments heighten stress among high school students, particularly in non-native English environments, as the fear of being evaluated can impair cognitive functioning. Similarly, Bibi et al. (2024) argue that oral exams provoke anxiety due to their spontaneous and high-stakes nature. Additionally, Ringeisen et al. (2018) highlighted that oral exams can cause significant psychological and physiological stress responses, potentially hindering students' performance.

Students' fear of negative evaluation before the implementation of the preparation strategy is presented in **Table 1.3**. The composite mean of 3.71 indicates a high level of fear associated with being judged by teachers and peers. While students expressed concern about negative judgment, avoidance of participation was not strongly evident,

suggesting internal conflict rather than withdrawal. This implies that students recognize the importance of participation despite apprehension.

The highest indicator is “I worry that my teacher will judge me negatively,” with a weighted mean of 4.09, verbally described as Agree, indicating a High level of anxiety. This shows that students experience significant social pressure related to academic performance and fear disappointing someone in a position of authority. This stems from teachers’ judgments often impact students’ grades and self-worth, which increases their worry and anxiety. On the other hand, the lowest indicator is “I avoid answering questions to prevent making mistakes,” which showed an “Undecided” response, implying mixed feelings about withdrawing from participation. This highlights that while students are anxious, they do not completely avoid speaking since they may recognize the importance of participating in class or feel motivated to overcome their fears.

These findings align with Gomez et al. (2023), who emphasized that negative peer evaluation strongly predicts public speaking anxiety, especially in collectivist cultures where maintaining social image is crucial. This shows that students often fear being mocked or misunderstood by their peers, which can increase anxiety. Moreover, Cheng et al. (2023) found that teachers’ non-verbal feedback and tone can either ease or worsen students’ self-perception during oral tasks, which affects their confidence. In addition, Aricheta (2024) reported that students who fear being judged do not always avoid participation outright; instead, they experience emotional indecision and internal conflict that disrupt their ability to respond confidently.

Meanwhile, the level of anxiety prior to the intervention in terms of comfort in speaking English is reflected in **Table 1.4**. The composite mean of 3.67 indicates a generally high level of comfort, although hesitation remains in certain aspects. Students showed strong willingness to take risks and try new vocabulary, but were less confident in clearly communicating their ideas. This gap highlights that motivation does not always translate into confidence, particularly when accuracy and clarity are involved.

The highest indicator is “I am willing to take risks and try new vocabulary,” with a weighted mean of 4.22, verbally described as Strongly Agree, indicating a Very High level of comfort and motivation to improve. This implies that students are motivated and eager to engage in learning despite challenges, likely influenced by positive reinforcement from teachers and a supportive classroom environment that promotes experimentation with language, which boosts their willingness to take risks. Alternatively, the lowest indicator is “I believe I can communicate my ideas clearly,” with a weighted mean of 3.17, verbally described as Undecided, reflecting a Moderate level of anxiety. This reflects that although students are willing to try, they lack full confidence in their ability to communicate effectively. Hesitation and self-doubt may arise from concerns about making mistakes, mispronunciation, or being misunderstood, which can undermine their clarity and fluency. The gap between motivation and self-assessed competence indicates that eagerness to participate is tempered by anxiety related to accuracy and clarity. This uncertainty may also stem from limited opportunities to engage in authentic English conversations or previous experiences of critical feedback that lowered their confidence.

These findings are supported by Hu and Wang (2023), who emphasized that willingness to communicate does not always equate to confidence, noting that students often lack trust in their grammar and pronunciation despite eagerness to speak. Similarly, Soriano and Co (2022) found that students in non-English-speaking countries practice speaking privately but hesitate in public interactions due to fear of embarrassment. Furthermore, Bordios et al. (2023) revealed that many students experience speaking anxiety due to fear of being judged and prefer strategies that foster a supportive and low-pressure environment to improve oral communication skills.

Following the implementation of the preparation strategy, students' communication apprehension was reassessed, as shown in **Table 2.1**. The composite mean decreased to 3.31, indicating a moderate level of anxiety and an improvement from pre-test results. While difficulty in organizing thoughts persisted, students showed reduced avoidance of speaking situations, reflecting increased confidence and willingness to engage. This improvement suggests that the preparation strategy was effective in mitigating communication apprehension.

The highest indicator is "I struggle to find the right words when speaking in front of a group," with a mean of 3.52, verbally described as Agree, indicating a High level of anxiety. This signifies that students still experience difficulty organizing their thoughts when speaking in front of others. This could stem from nervousness, limited vocabulary recall under pressure, or a lack of confidence in expressing ideas spontaneously. This suggests that, while preparation strategy reduced communication apprehension, students may still require targeted interventions to improve fluency and reduce mental blocks during speaking situations. On the other hand, the lowest item is "I try to avoid situations where I have to talk in front of others" with a mean of 3.04, which is interpreted as Undecided, indicating a Moderate level of anxiety. This implies that students are not actively avoiding public speaking but may still feel hesitant. The moderate response suggests that while fear is present, it is not strong enough to result in complete avoidance. This could be a sign of progress, as students might be beginning to build resilience and willingness to face speaking situations, especially with the support of a structured preparation strategy.

These results support the findings of Kuluşaklı and Genç (2024), who found that even with structured preparation, students may still experience communication apprehension in real-time interactions due to gaps in communicative competence. Similarly, Zou (2024) found that among senior high school students, communication apprehension was a significant component of speaking anxiety, and interventions targeting this area effectively reduced overall anxiety levels. Additionally, Thu and Tran (2024) concluded that communication apprehension can significantly hinder students' willingness to speak in public, especially when they lack prior speaking experience or training.

Students' test anxiety after the implementation of the preparation strategy is presented in **Table 2.2**. The composite mean of 3.52 indicates that test anxiety remained high despite a slight reduction. Fear of making mistakes and anxiety during graded

speeches continued to be the strongest concerns. This suggests that evaluative anxiety remains a challenge even after preparation, requiring continued support and exposure.

The composite mean of 3.52 falls under the High level of anxiety. This implies that while the preparation strategy had a positive effect in slightly reducing students' test-related anxiety, the fear associated with being formally assessed remains a significant challenge. This persistent anxiety may affect students' overall performance and confidence during graded speaking tasks, potentially hindering their ability to fully demonstrate their skills. Therefore, continued practice, exposure, and targeted anxiety-reduction techniques may be needed to bring this anxiety down to more manageable levels. Meanwhile, the lowest indicators, "I feel stressed when delivering a presentation" and "I find it difficult to concentrate during a speaking test," both have a mean of 3.39, which falls under Undecided and signifies a Moderate level of anxiety. Though slightly lower, these values still reflect internal struggles when under performance evaluation. This connotes that while students may be gradually adjusting to the pressures of public speaking, cognitive and emotional challenges remain areas of concern.

These results are aligned with Wang (2020), who highlighted that test anxiety is closely associated with academic procrastination and persistent stress under evaluation. Pontillias and Rodrigo (2024) reported that high school students often experience elevated test anxiety during oral assessments, and structured preparation can mitigate this anxiety. Similarly, Zhang et al. (2022) emphasized that while certain interventions may reduce anxiety, the stress of evaluation remains a core challenge for students during test performance.

With regard to fear of negative evaluation, post-intervention results are reflected in **Table 2.3**. The composite mean of 3.24 indicates a moderate level of anxiety, suggesting a reduction compared to pre-test results. However, hesitation due to fear of criticism persisted. This suggests that while the preparation strategy helped reduce anxiety, additional interventions are needed to further strengthen students' confidence.

The results show that the highest indicator is "I hesitate to participate because I fear criticism," with a mean of 3.43, described as Agree, indicating a High level of anxiety. This evokes that fear of negative feedback from others continues to impact students' participation. Such fear can limit students' willingness to engage actively in class discussions and presentations, potentially hindering their learning and growth in public speaking skills. On the other hand, the lowest item is "I avoid answering questions to prevent making mistakes" with a weighted mean of 2.96, which is interpreted as Undecided, indicating Moderate level of anxiety. Although moderate, this still suggests that many students are hesitant to engage due to fear of being wrong. This hesitation can reduce opportunities for active participation and practice, which are crucial for improving public speaking skills, indicating a need for strategies that create a safe space for risk-taking and learning from mistakes.

These findings are consistent with Pabro-Maquidato and Lourdes College (2021), who found that fear of negative feedback significantly affects oral performance and participation in public speaking settings. Moreover, Zabidin et al. (2023) reported that high levels of motivation can lessen the effects of fear of negative evaluation, but the presence

of fear still persists among students with lower confidence. Additionally, Huda et al. (2022) found that fear of negative evaluation significantly impacts students' public speaking anxiety, and targeted interventions can reduce this fear, leading to improved academic performance.

On a more positive note, students' comfort in speaking English after the intervention is presented in **Table 2.4**. The composite mean of 3.94 indicates a high level of comfort, with students reporting increased enjoyment in practicing speaking and greater willingness to take risks. However, initiating spontaneous conversations remained challenging. Taken together, these results suggest that the preparation strategy effectively enhanced confidence and motivation toward English communication.

The results imply that the highest indicators are "I enjoy practicing and improving my speaking skills," with a weighted mean of 4.57, and "I am willing to take risks and try new vocabulary," with a mean of 4.43, both described as Strongly Agree, indicating a Very High level of comfort. These findings suggest that the preparation strategy is particularly effective in building positive attitudes and motivation toward learning English. This increased comfort likely fosters greater participation and confidence in real-life communication, encouraging students to overcome anxiety and actively engage in English speaking opportunities. The lowest 3.30 indicator is "I feel comfortable initiating conversations in English," categorized as Undecided, reflecting a Moderate level of comfort in spontaneous English use. This connotes that while students may feel confident practicing prepared speeches or rehearsed content, they still face challenges when required to engage in impromptu or natural conversations, highlighting an area for further support and practice.

These findings are aligned with the study of Ghafar (2023) that supports the idea that active preparation boosts students' self-confidence and engagement in using English in academic contexts. Similarly, Cagot et al. (2023) highlighted that students' comfort in speaking English is influenced by their confidence and fear of making mistakes and that supportive strategies can improve their comfort levels. Furthermore, Ong and Zambas (2021) designed a training program to reduce public speaking anxiety, which significantly improved students' confidence and engagement in using English.

To further examine the effectiveness of the preparation strategy, differences in communication apprehension before and after the intervention are shown in **Table 3.1**. The significant decrease from the pre-test median to the post-test median indicates that the strategy was effective in reducing communication apprehension.

The results demonstrate that the pre-test had a median of 4.0, indicating a high level of anxiety, with students expressing significant difficulty in communicating effectively in front of a group. After the implementation of the preparation strategy, the post-test median dropped to 3.4, reflecting a noticeable decrease in communication apprehension. This reduction is statistically significant, with a p-value of 0.003, indicating that the preparation strategy effectively helped students feel more comfortable communicating in public.

These results align with the findings of Ebrahimi et al. (2019), who conducted a meta-analysis and found that psychological interventions, including preparation strategies, significantly reduced fear of public speaking. Similarly, Ulfah (2024) found that structured speaking drills significantly reduced communication apprehension among students. Furthermore, Gürbüz and Cabaroğlu (2021) highlighted that task-based speaking activities and oral preparation strategies boosted students' confidence, reducing anxiety in speaking situations.

The difference in students' test anxiety before and after the intervention is presented in **Table 3.2**. The significant reduction in median scores confirms that the preparation strategy effectively reduced students' anxiety related to oral assessments.

The findings revealed that the pre-test revealed a median of 4.2, indicating a very high level of anxiety surrounding test situations. After the preparation strategy was implemented, the post-test median decreased to 3.6, signaling a significant reduction in test anxiety. The p-value of <0.001 , which is below the 0.05 threshold, confirms that this change is statistically significant. This suggests that the preparation strategy was effective in reducing students' anxiety related to oral assessments.

These results are supported by Neufeld et al. (2020), who found that cognitive-behavioral therapies, including preparatory exercises, significantly reduced test anxiety. Additionally, Kahlon et al. (2019) demonstrated that interventions like virtual reality exposure therapy effectively reduced anxiety related to public speaking assessments. Furthermore, a quasi-experimental study by Yusefzadeh et al. (2019) found that study preparation significantly reduced test anxiety and improved performance among students.

Likewise, the difference in fear of negative evaluation before and after the intervention is reflected in **Table 3.3**. The significant decrease in median scores indicates that the preparation strategy helped reduce students' fear of judgment.

The results display that the pre-test median was 3.8, indicating a moderate fear of judgment or criticism. However, following the preparation strategy, the post-test median dropped to 3.4, suggesting a decrease in this fear. With a p-value of 0.024, which is below the 0.05 significance level, the difference is statistically significant. This indicates that the preparation strategy is effective in helping students reduce their fear of negative evaluation.

This aligns with the findings of Busch et al. (2023), who noted that fear of negative evaluation could greatly hinder participation, especially in marginalized student populations, and that intervention is necessary to reduce this fear. Downing et al. (2020) also reported that alleviating fear of negative evaluation enhanced students' confidence and participation, which was supported by the results in this study. Furthermore, a study by ul Huda et al. (2024) highlighted that fear of negative evaluation could greatly hinder participation, especially in marginalized student populations, and that intervention was necessary to reduce this fear.

In contrast, the difference in students' comfort in speaking English before and after the intervention is shown in **Table 3.4**. Although there was a slight increase in the post-test median, the difference was not statistically significant. This suggests that comfort in speaking English requires sustained exposure and long-term practice.

The findings suggest that the pre-test median was 3.8, reflecting a moderate level of comfort, while the post-test median slightly increased to 4.0, indicating a slight improvement in comfort. However, with a p-value of 0.171, which exceeds the significance level of 0.05, this difference is not statistically significant. This suggests that while students may have become more comfortable with managing anxiety, their overall fluency and comfort in using English remained largely unchanged.

These results are supported by Macdonald (2025), who emphasized that improving language comfort requires immersive, consistent practice, particularly with language exposure beyond the preparatory phase. Similarly, Ghafar (2023) concluded that while preparation programs improve fluency, they often fall short in addressing deep-seated discomfort related to speaking English. Additionally, Pabro-Maquidato (2021) found that Filipino university students experience significant emotional and physiological anxiety when speaking English, often due to fear of negative feedback. The study highlighted that coping strategies such as reading English materials and seeking feedback helped students gradually build confidence and comfort in speaking English.

Lastly, the relationship between age and public speaking anxiety is presented in **Table 4.1**. The results indicate no significant relationship, suggesting that public speaking anxiety is independent of age among senior high school students. This finding aligns with Quinn and Goody (2019), Chen (2024), and Tatlı and Karadağ (2024).

Finally, the relationship between sex and public speaking anxiety is shown in **Table 4.2**. The results show no significant relationship ($p = 0.265 > \alpha = 0.05$), indicating that public speaking anxiety is independent of sex. This suggests that both male and female students experience similar levels of anxiety when it comes to public speaking.

This finding is supported by Riski and Sangmin-Michelle (2024), who observed no consistent pattern of gender-based differences in public speaking anxiety across multiple studies, highlighting that psychological readiness and individual experience play a more prominent role. Dueck (2021) also found no significant variation between male and female pre-service teachers' anxiety levels, emphasizing that intervention strategies, not sex, made the difference. Similarly, Chen (2024) reported that both male and female learners benefited equally from technology-enhanced language learning, underscoring the importance of instructional design over demographic factors.

Conclusions

This study found that the preparation strategy implemented among Grade 11 STEM students was effective in significantly reducing public speaking anxiety, particularly in the areas of communication apprehension, test anxiety, and fear of negative evaluation. After the intervention, students demonstrated improved confidence, emotional regulation, and self-control when speaking in public, confirming that structured preparation activities

such as outlining, guided rehearsal, and relaxation techniques are practical tools for managing anxiety. Although students' comfort in speaking English increased slightly, the change was not statistically significant, suggesting that language comfort may require longer exposure and continued use of English in authentic communication settings. The findings also revealed that public speaking anxiety affected students regardless of age and sex, indicating that PSA is a common experience among learners. Overall, the results highlight the value of integrating preparation-based approaches into instructional practice to strengthen students' speaking performance, self-awareness, and resilience in academic communication.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the researchers recommend that students consistently engage in preparation practices such as outlining, rehearsing, and relaxation exercises to manage anxiety before public speaking tasks. Developing these habits can enhance composure, confidence, and overall speaking performance. Teachers are encouraged to incorporate structured preparation activities in oral communication lessons and provide guided practice sessions, constructive feedback, and positive reinforcement to help students gain assurance when delivering speeches. School administrators may also initiate training programs, seminars, or school-wide activities that promote effective communication and public speaking, thereby fostering a supportive environment where students can participate without fear or hesitation.

Moreover, parents play a vital role in reducing public speaking anxiety by offering emotional support, encouragement, and opportunities for open communication at home. Their involvement helps students feel more confident and secure when expressing themselves in public settings. Future researchers are encouraged to replicate this study using larger and more diverse samples across different academic strands to validate the findings further. They may also explore alternative interventions or examine the long-term effects of preparation strategy on students' confidence and anxiety levels in public speaking contexts.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The conduct of this study was strictly governed by the ethical standards of the researchers. Informed consent of participation was provided by all participants after a full explanation of the aims, methods, potential risks, and benefits of the research. The participation was purely voluntary, and the students were allowed to pull out from the study at any moment without facing any sort of inconvenience. The privacy and confidentiality of the respondents were carefully protected, and all data gathered were treated with respect and kept strictly confidential. The researchers also ensured that no form of physical, emotional, or psychological harm came to any participant. Plagiarism was completely avoided by virtue of proper citing and acknowledgment of all used sources. Furthermore, the researchers made certain that the data and findings were interpreted in an impartial manner, without bias or external influence. The results obtained were used only for academic and research purposes, in accordance with the ethical regulations of Foundation University's Ethics Committee

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